

Rac-5e

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	XT-3-10-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	1207
Vial:	70	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 3 10 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	16.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	12/7/2021 11:20:24 AM CST		
Date Processed:	12/7/2021 2:43:31 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	10.593	1898237	50.05	95082
2	12.349	1894801	49.95	

Asy-5e

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-18-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	35	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 3 18
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	12/7/2021 10:58:19 AM CST		
Date Processed:	12/7/2021 2:45:28 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	10.595	8458518	97.29	422855
2	12.357	235784	2.71	10067